

Chemiluminescent Method for Determination of Low Concentration of Hydrogen Peroxide

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A chemiluminescent method for the estimation of low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide in solution phase is described. This is based on the well known chemiluminescent oxidation of luminol in alkaline medium in the presence of Cu(II) as catalyst, and employs only $\sim 2 \text{ cm}^3$ of sample solution. Interference due to dissolved oxygen was found to be eliminated by purging with argon gas in a cold trap at 0° . The log-log plot of chemiluminescence response versus H_2O_2 concentration was found to be linear over more than five orders of magnitude increase in the latter. The lowest detectable concentration of $\sim 2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was found to be limited not by the instrument response but by the background concentration of H_2O_2 present (even) in triple distilled water (TDW) used for making up the solutions. This could be lowered by an order of magnitude by freshly distilling the TDW over MnO_2 , but was found to revert to the higher value on keeping in contact with ambient air and light. The time dependence of the chemiluminescence response was exponential, the half life being affected considerably by impurities present in the sample.

THERE are a number of analytical situations requiring the accurate estimation of sub-parts per million concentration of hydrogen peroxide. These are to name a few, hydrogen peroxide present in natural waters¹, in the ambient and polluted atmosphere originating from photochemical reactions^{2,3}, γ -radiolysis of aqueous solutions⁴ and photolysis of aqueous solutions both in homogeneous solutions and catalysed at surfaces^{5,6}. Among the commonly used analytical methods even the most sensitive spectrophotometric ones based on the formation of intensely absorbing coloured compounds by reaction with H_2O_2 can measure concentrations down to at most $10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ under the best conditions. It is in this connection that chemiluminescent methods have attracted considerable attention. With the availability of extremely low dark current photomultiplier tubes and photon counting instrumentation it is now possible to detect very low intensities of light. Assuming a detection capability of 10^4 photons (above background) in a cell volume of 2 cm^3 and assuming chemical, quantum and geometrical efficiencies of 0.1 each, one can detect in principle a concentration as low as $10^{-14} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ provided a suitable and fast (light emission being complete in about a minute) chemiluminescent reaction is available.

Luminol, (5-amino-2,3-dihydro-1,4-phthalazine-dione)^{1,2,8-12}, bis (2,4,6-trichlorophenyl-oxalate)¹³, lucigenin (N,N'-di-methyldiacridinium dinitrate)¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and siloxene¹⁸ are some of the compounds known to undergo chemiluminescent reactions with H_2O_2 and particularly the first two

have been employed for the detection and estimation of low concentrations of H_2O_2 . Although a photographic plate can be used as a detector of the luminescence, there are only a few reports of this¹⁹⁻²⁵ and the minimum detectable concentration was $\sim 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The photomultiplier tube is a much more sensitive light detector and the vast majority of the chemiluminescent methods for the detection of H_2O_2 have employed this device. The major reported applications have been in the fields of analysis of H_2O_2 in natural water¹ and in the ambient atmosphere^{2,3,8}. Operationally, both injection⁸ and continuous flow^{1,2,9-12} techniques have been employed. The former is simpler in practice and forms the basis of the present work, which was aimed at developing a suitable apparatus for this purpose, assessing its suitability for the analysis of low concentration of H_2O_2 in aqueous solutions and ambient air and identifying the parameters affecting the lowest detection limit.

Experimental

The apparatus employed in the present work is shown schematically in Fig 1. The sample solution is injected through a light tight injection port by means of a hypodermic syringe into the luminol+catalyst solution taken in a quartz 1 cm rectangular spectrophotometer cuvette mounted directly in front of the PMT detector in an integral light tight housing made of aluminium. The PMT detector employed is the relatively inexpensive RCA-1P28 having a photocathode response (250-500 nm) compatible with the spectrum of the light emitted in

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the apparatus for the study of chemiluminescent oxidation of Luminol by H_2O_2 in solution.

the reaction between H_2O_2 and luminol (λ_{max} 435 nm). The high voltage for the PMT was obtained from an 'Aplab' 7341P model power supply. The anode current from the PMT was amplified in an 'ECIL' model EA815 FET input electrometer amplifier and recorded on a 'Digilog' model 5211-5 omniscrite potentiometric strip chart recorder.

All reagent solutions were made in triple distilled water (TDW), which was routinely prepared in our laboratory by distillation of still distilled water over acid-dichromate and then over alkaline permanganate. Standard solution (10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) of hydrogen peroxide was prepared by dilution of 6% (v/v) stock solution with TDW and checked against standardised permanganate solution by titration. Stock solutions of cupric nitrate and luminol were prepared by well established procedures^{1-3,6}. Stock solutions of luminol and H_2O_2 were stored in the refrigerator to minimize decomposition over a period of time.

Our detailed studies employed Cu(II) as the catalyst. A working solution of 7.2×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} luminol containing 4.5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} Cu(II) was prepared in NaOH to give a final pH of 12.9-13 as and when required. All other chemicals such as NaOH, $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, $NiSO_4$, $CoSO_4$, $FeSO_4$, NH_3 etc. were AnalaR grade and were used without further purification.

For chemiluminescence studies one cm^3 of the luminol solution containing the appropriate catalyst and pH adjusted to the optimum was taken in the 1 cm quartz spectrophotometer cuvette mounted in the apparatus as shown in Fig. 1. Into this was quickly (in ~ 5 sec) injected $2 cm^3$ of the standard or test solution containing H_2O_2 . The intensity of the light emitted in the chemiluminescent reaction was monitored as a function of time on the strip chart recorder. A typical recorder trace is shown in Fig. 2.

Results and Discussion

The reproducibility of the chemiluminescence response as a function of time is very good when

Fig. 2. Recorder trace of chemiluminescence for a 10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 solution in QDW (Amplifier setting at 100 mV full scale, recorder setting at 10 mV full scale).

recorder traces such as Fig. 2 are compared for the same concentration of H_2O_2 . The initial response during the first five seconds after injection (shown as a very sharp peak in Fig. 2) is a composite of the response due to light emitted from the chemiluminescent reaction, light leakage during injection and mechanical disturbance due to the injection process itself, and is rather irreproducible. The subsequent decay, however, is quite reproducible. For quantitative estimation the chemiluminescence response was measured by reading the signal intensity of curves such as the one in Fig. 2 at a fixed time (15 sec) after sample injection.

Different transition metal ion catalysts were tried under conditions reported in the literature to be the most optimum for the H_2O_2 -luminol chemiluminescent reaction. Among these the Cu^{2+} catalyst was found to yield the maximum chemiluminescence response and has been used throughout the rest of our work.

Although anions such as bromide have been reported^{2,6} to enhance the chemiluminescence output of the H_2O_2 +luminol reaction with Cr^{3+} as catalyst, such an effect was not observed with Cu^{2+} under the conditions employed even upto $2 mol dm^{-3}$ of Br^- concentration.

The variation of the chemiluminescence response with H_2O_2 concentration is shown in Fig. 3 on log-log scale. This is found to be linear over at least four orders of magnitude in H_2O_2 concentration. In fact, the upper limit is set by the maximum current readable on the least sensitive range of the amplifier used.

In the blank TDW the current due to the chemiluminescence is 1.5×10^{-8} amp (equivalent to $\sim 5 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2), which is about 15 times

higher than the dark current of the 1P28 PMT employed in the present work. Therefore the present set up is inherently capable of measuring H_2O_2 concentration down to 10^{-9} mol dm^{-3} . The practical lower limit is therefore due to the background response from the TDW.

Possible sources of this background luminescence in water are presence of dissolved oxygen and H_2O_2 itself or other peroxy compounds. Chemiluminescent reaction between luminol and O_2 in

Fig. 3. Calibration plot for H_2O_2 estimation in solution. A-Fresh QDW, Ar saturated (kept in the dark or in ambient light for any length of time); B-Fresh as well as stored QDW (in a closed bottle); C-Fresh QDW, O_2 saturated and kept in a closed container in ambient light; D-Fresh QDW kept in an open container in ambient light for 4 hr.

alkaline DMSO medium has in fact been suggested²⁷ as a sensitive method for determination of low concentration of oxygen (as low as 10^{-11} mol dm^{-3}). The aqueous luminol + Cu(II) system employed in the present study was in fact found to give a chemiluminescence response when gaseous air or oxygen was injected. This was not due to any artefact of injection as argon gas similarly injected did not show any response. Purging of TDW with argon gas (at ~ 100 cm^3 min^{-1} with the sample immersed in ice bath to avoid loss of H_2O_2) before injection lowered the background response from the equivalent of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 to $\sim 2 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm^{-3} thus indicating that at least part of this is due to dissolved oxygen (concentration $\sim 2 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3}) in TDW.

In order to find out whether the remaining part of the background response in TDW is due to H_2O_2 , the TDW was subjected to one more distillation over MnO_2 and the resulting distillate (referred to as quadruple distilled water, QDW) was found to give a background response equivalent to 5×10^{-9} mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 . This further reduced to

2×10^{-9} mol dm^{-3} equivalent H_2O_2 on argon purging. The latter value together with the value of $\sim 2 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm^{-3} equivalent of H_2O_2 in TDW would lead us to infer that our laboratory TDW contains 18×10^{-9} mol dm^{-3} equivalent of H_2O_2 or some other compound, capable of luminescence, being destroyed by reaction with MnO_2 at 373 K. Interestingly, the background value of 2×10^{-9} mol dm^{-3} equivalent of H_2O_2 in QDW was found to return to the TDW value when left overnight in the laboratory in the open. Detailed investigations were carried out to identify the causes responsible for this behaviour. The results of these studies indicated that pure water (QDW) gets contaminated by formation of H_2O_2 (or some other species capable of undergoing a chemiluminescent reaction with luminol + Cu^{2+} system) when exposed to ambient light and air or oxygen. The extent of this was found to be more when it was exposed in an open container. Although these results do not positively indicate this species to be H_2O_2 , an analysis of the decay profile of the chemiluminescence response (*vide infra*) would suggest that it is most probably H_2O_2 .

The chemiluminescent decay profiles for QDW and TDW injected into the luminol + Cu(II) system are compared with that for authentic H_2O_2 samples in Fig. 4 on semilog scale. The similarity amongst the four is quite evident. Further, it is seen that although the decay is truly exponential the negative slope of the semilog plot decreases with increasing H_2O_2 concentration which would imply a somewhat complex kinetics.

Fig. 4. Semilog plot of recorder response against time for different samples of water under identical conditions: ●-Fresh QDW, Ar saturated; □-Fresh TDW, Ar saturated; ○- 8.3×10^{-8} mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 sample; △- 25×10^{-8} mol dm^{-3} H_2O_2 sample; ×-Tap water; ▼-DW from still; ■- O_2 saturated TDW.

Whatever be the species that is really responsible for the background chemiluminescence observed

when pure water is injected into the luminol + Cu(II) system, its implication in the analysis of low concentrations of H_2O_2 by the chemiluminescent technique is important. Thus, if we are interested in measuring concentrations of the order of 10^{-8} mol dm^{-3} we must employ QDW for preparing the H_2O_2 solution and subtract the QDW blank response from the observed response for the sample. The luminol + Cu(II) reagent solution need not be prepared in QDW as any background would have decayed prior to injection provided that the reagent has been prepared in TDW and stored for some time.

We have found the present technique to be sufficiently sensitive to measure H_2O_2 present in the ambient atmosphere²⁹. Although the use of the luminol + catalyst system has been suggested to be usable for the analysis of the H_2O_2 in natural water¹, the presence of various other species can affect the chemiluminescence response in an unknown manner. For example, the decay of the response for tap water was found to be nonexponential whereas the response of distilled water fresh from the still exhibited a very slow decay (see Fig. 4). These differences as compared to the decay observed in the case of authentic H_2O_2 or that present in TDW or QDW could be due to either the quenching action of impurities present in the sample or their interferences with the reaction scheme leading to the generation of chemiluminescent species in the H_2O_2 + luminol reaction. It may be worth mentioning here that details of this reaction scheme as well as the identity of the luminescent species are not yet known. From the application point of view, however, it is important to establish first that the decay of the chemiluminescence response in the unknown system closely parallels that for authentic H_2O_2 before attempts are made for quantitative assay. In the absence of a convincingly good parallelism the first attempt should be to remove the interfering species by a preliminary separation scheme.

References

1. F. SHAW, *Analyst*, 1980, 105, 11.
2. G. L. KOK, T. P. HOLLER, M. B. LOPEZ, H. A. NACHTRIEB and M. YUAN, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, 12, 1072.
3. G. L. KOK, K. R. DARWALL, A. M. WINER, J. N. PRYDS, JR. and B. N. GAY, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, 12, 1077.
4. A. O. ALLEN in "Radiation Chemistry of Water and Aqueous Solutions", D. Van Nostrand and Co., 1961.
5. M. C. MARKHAM and K. J. LAIDLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 363.
6. D. R. DIXON and T. W. HEALY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, 24, 1193.
7. A. I. VOGEL in "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS and Longman, London, 1973, p. 295, 325.
8. W. A. ARMSTRONG and W. G. HUMPHREYS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, 43, 2576.
9. W. R. SEITZ, W. W. SUYDAM, D. M. HERCULES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1972, 44, 957.
10. T. G. BURDO and W. R. SEITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 47, 1639.
11. D. T. BOSTICK and D. M. HERCULES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 47, 447.
12. J. P. AUSES, S. L. COOK and J. T. MALOY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 47, 244.
13. D. C. WILLIAMS, G. F. MUFF and W. R. SEITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, 48, 1003.
14. K. GLEN and N. PRITSCH, *Angew. Chem.*, 1935, 48, 57.
15. J. R. TOTTER, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1964, 3, 231.
16. F. MCCAPRA and D. G. RICHARDSON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, 3167.
17. F. MCCAPRA, D. G. RICHARDSON and Y. C. CHANG, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1965, 4, 1111.
18. U. ISACSSON and G. WETTERMARK, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 68, 399.
19. A. K. BABKO and N. M. LUKOVSKAYA, *J. Anal. Chem. USSR*, 1965, 20, 1153.
20. A. K. BABKO and N. M. LUKOVSKAYA, *J. Anal. Chem. USSR*, 1962, 17, 47.
21. A. K. BABKO and N. M. LUKOVSKAYA, *Zavod. Lab.*, 1963, 29, 404.
22. A. K. BABKO, L. I. DUBOVENKO and L. S. MIKHAILOVA, *Metody. Anal. Khim. R. Rakt. Prep.*, Mo 13, 1969, 139.
23. L. I. DUBOVENKO and CHAN TI HUU, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1969, 35, 637.
24. L. I. DUBOVENKO and T. A. BOGOSLOVSKAYA, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1971, 37, 1057.
25. L. I. DUBOVENKO and CHAN TI HUU, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1969, 35, 957.
26. D. E. BAVER and H. H. PATTERSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1979, 51, 2288.
27. A. BURR and D. MEYERALL, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1968, 153, 614.
28. J. R. PARTINGTON in "General and Inorganic Chemistry", Macmillan and Co. Ltd., London, 1954, p. 650.⁴
29. T. N. DAS, P. N. MOORTHY and K. N. RAO, results to be published.